

3D-Printed Models as a Prelude: Enhancing Comprehension of VR Software City Visualizations

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Abstract—Background: Virtual Reality (VR) visualizations have shown potential in enhancing the understanding of software systems through immersive city metaphors. However, the impact of combining physical 3D-printed models with VR environments (Hybrid Mode) on software comprehension remains underexplored.

Objective/Aim: This Registered Report aims to evaluate whether a Hybrid Mode (3D-printed models combined with VR) leads to faster and more accurate comprehension of software projects and their metrics compared to a purely Virtual Mode (VR visualization only). Specifically, we will analyze the correctness and time to completion of software comprehension and code exploration tasks under different time constraints (5, 10, and 15 minutes).

Method: A controlled experiment will be conducted with participants randomly assigned to one of two modes: Hybrid or Virtual. Both setups will use the city metaphor to represent software project metrics, particularly code smells. Tasks will be designed to test the participants' ability to comprehend the software structure and locate smells in the code. Data will be collected and analyzed to compare performance across the two modes under different time limits, providing insights into the effectiveness of combining physical and virtual representations in software visualization.

Index Terms—city metaphor, software visualization, CODECITY, 3D printing, virtual reality, code smells

I. INTRODUCTION

The primary goal of this study is to evaluate whether the integration of physical 3D-printed models in conjunction with Virtual Reality (VR) visualizations (Hybrid Mode) leads to a better comprehension of software metrics when compared to VR visualizations alone (Virtual Mode). We specifically focus on visualizing metrics related to Scratch programming projects using the city metaphor, a well-established technique in software visualization.

This study aims to determine whether the Hybrid Mode improves participants' ability to perform software comprehension and exploration tasks, particularly under strict time constraints. Comprehension in this context refers to the ability of participants to accurately and efficiently analyze and interpret project structure and code smells within a limited timeframe.

Thus, we extend prior work by combining 3D printed visualizations with virtual reality (VR) to explore their impact on understanding and analyzing software projects. Building on research that emphasizes the value of multimodal data visualization in enhancing user comprehension [1], [2], we

hypothesize that hybrid approaches, which integrate tangible and immersive elements, can improve task efficiency and correctness.

We will leverage on BABIAXR [3], [4] for constructing city metaphors in 3D and VR. We have chosen Scratch, a block programming language that is very popular in education as the technology of our experiment. Scratch has been chosen for this experiment as a medium to test the visualization approach due to its simplicity and small project size. These characteristics make it ideal for constructing clear and interpretable visualizations while focusing on the analysis of project metrics. Although Scratch is not a professional programming language, its use here enables the rapid evaluation of visualization techniques applicable to broader contexts. Moreover, according to the TIOBE index, Scratch has ranked 9th as the most used language in March 2024¹, being thus one of the most used programming languages worldwide. It is a block-based programming language that has revolutionized computational thinking (CT) [5] education by enabling young learners to create interactive stories, games, and animations. Its constructionist approach supports creativity and individual learning trajectories [6]. Automated tools like Dr. Scratch offer metrics for evaluating CT based on Scratch projects [7]. Dr. Scratch analyzes code blocks to assess dimensions such as abstraction, logic, and parallelism, facilitating large-scale and consistent CT evaluations in diverse educational contexts [8].

Recent advancements in educational technologies have highlighted the importance of combining interactive tools like Scratch with innovative visualization methods to enhance CT education. For instance, integrating game-based learning (GBL) environments with Scratch has shown potential to improve student engagement and foster STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) skills [9]. Visualizing complex data in immersive environments, such as virtual reality (VR), offers new opportunities to represent abstract concepts in tangible ways, potentially bridging gaps in understanding [1], [2]. We argue that by translating Scratch project metrics into 3D city metaphors within VR, educators and learners can explore these metrics in a more intuitive and engaging manner, fostering deeper comprehension of programming principles and CT dimensions. If the results of

¹<https://www.tiobe.com/tiobe-index/scratch/>

our experiment show promising results, efforts can be devoted in future research to study the impact of hybrid approaches in professional software development environments, adapting our experiment to larger codebases.

II. BACKGROUND

A. 3D Printing Data Visualization

Three-dimensional (3D) printing has emerged as a powerful tool for data visualization, offering tangible representations of complex datasets. Research highlights its potential in map and geography visualization [1], while applications in archaeology show how combining 3D printing with immersive visualization improves the perception of ancient artifacts [10]. Similarly, scientific visualization studies demonstrate its value in multivariate biomarker data representation [2] and neuroscience education, where 3D neuron models aid in structural understanding [11].

Beyond scientific research, 3D printing has significant educational implications, particularly in STEM learning. It has been successfully integrated into engineering education, improving student engagement and understanding [12]. Studies also show its effectiveness in visualizing abstract mathematical concepts [13] and its positive impact on student motivation and skill development [14]. Furthermore, advancements in augmented reality (AR) expand its interactive potential, enabling printed data visualizations to be dynamically explored [15], while tangible interaction approaches enhance data interpretation [16]. These works underline 3D printing's role in enhancing comprehension across scientific, educational, and mathematical disciplines, demonstrating its effectiveness in bridging gaps between abstract data and intuitive understanding.

B. VR BABIAXR Visualizations

The goal of a VR environment is to leverage the immersive and spatial capabilities it provides. We will use A-Frame for the development of VR visualizations through the platform BABIAXR [3], [4], creating a scene where the visualizations of the Scratch projects and their metrics will be organized. BABIAXR provides a set of different 3D visualizations, including some with three axes (e.g., bars, cylinders, bubbles) to represent depth, height, and width in the same visualization. This allows for a more comprehensive representation of the data, offering an additional metric compared to common 2D visualizations. BABIAXR also provides 3D treemap visualizations that can be used to represent the metaphor of a city of code.

C. Related studies

Scratch software metrics

Automated CT metrics have proven to be essential tools for assessing CT development in Scratch projects. Dr. Scratch, introduced by Moreno-León and Robles, has played a pivotal role in formal and informal educational settings by providing structured assessments of CT skills, mapping observable coding practices to key dimensions such as abstraction, logic,

and flow control [7]. Dr. Scratch 2.0 expanded on this by introducing personalized rubrics and batch assessments, improving adaptability in evaluating diverse educational needs [17]. These advancements enhanced the scalability of CT assessments while integrating meaningful feedback mechanisms to support student learning. Recent studies have also demonstrated that applying CT metrics in game-based learning (GBL) environments fosters skill improvement through iterative project comparisons [9].

Virtual Reality

VR facilitates spatial understanding and complex data analysis across various domains, including medical visualization [18], [19], shape perception [20], and paleontology [21]. Its ability to support multidimensional data exploration has been widely studied in fields like scientific data visualization [22]–[24]. Research highlights VR's potential to enhance interaction with complex datasets [25]–[28], although caution has been advised against unwarranted 3D usage, which can introduce cognitive overload without clear benefits [29], [30]. The city metaphor, originally proposed by Munro et al. [31] and expanded by Wettel et al. [32], has been adapted to VR environments [33], with comparative studies analyzing on-screen vs. VR-based implementations [34], [35]. Traditionally applied to object-oriented programming languages, this metaphor effectively maps class hierarchies and package structures to buildings and districts. However, since Scratch lacks a traditional object hierarchy, our approach adapts the city metaphor to sprites, scripts, and blocks, focusing on complexity, smells, and modularity to ensure meaningful visual representations.

3D printing and XR

3D printing and extended reality (XR) have been widely explored for their ability to enhance spatial understanding and user interaction. In medical applications, studies have shown that combining VR and 3D printing improves preoperative visualization [36] and enhances diagnosis techniques in fields such as congenital heart disease [37]. Beyond medicine, cultural heritage studies have leveraged XR and 3D printing to enrich visitor experiences through interactive models [38]. From an educational perspective, XR technologies support spatial learning and STEM education, with research highlighting educators' interest in AR, VR, and 3D modeling [39] and their role in developing mathematical and spatial reasoning skills [40]. Moreover, CAD and AI advancements continue to expand XR and 3D printing integration [41]. Despite these advances, the use of 3D printing in software engineering remains underexplored. Fittkau et al. [42] demonstrated the potential benefits of physical 3D models for software comprehension, offering tangible representations of software structures. However, their study did not incorporate VR. Our study extends this approach by investigating the combination of physical 3D models with VR, aiming to assess how hybrid visualizations impact software comprehension, thereby filling an unexplored gap in the literature.

III. EXPERIMENT PLANNING

A. Goals

The experiment will address two key aspects:

- **Accuracy of Task Completion:** Evaluating whether the Hybrid Mode enables participants to identify and analyze software metrics, such as code smells, with higher correctness compared to the Virtual Mode.
- **Efficiency of Comprehension:** Assessing whether the Hybrid Mode leads to faster completion times for software comprehension tasks, particularly under shorter time constraints (e.g., 5 minutes).

We also aim to explore the interplay between task completion time and performance across the two modes. Specifically, we hypothesize that while the Hybrid Mode will outperform the Virtual Mode in shorter timeframes, the performance differences will diminish as participants are given more time to complete the tasks. This study also aims to provide empirical evidence for how hybrid visualization approaches impact the comprehension of software metrics, focusing on small-scale projects like those in Scratch as a controlled environment. The findings are expected to inform the design of tools applicable to larger, professional software systems, particularly in onboarding scenarios where initial project understanding is critical.

B. Hypotheses or Research Questions

This study aims to evaluate the impact of combining physical 3D-printed models with VR visualizations on the comprehension of software metrics in Scratch projects. The research questions (RQs) and their corresponding hypotheses (H) are as follows:

- **RQ1:** Does the Hybrid Mode lead to faster comprehension of software metrics compared to the Virtual Mode under shorter time constraints? (**H1:** Participants using the Hybrid Mode will complete tasks faster than those using the Virtual Mode when given limited time.)
- **RQ2:** Does the Hybrid Mode improve the accuracy of task completion compared to the Virtual Mode? (**H2:** Participants using the Hybrid Mode will achieve higher correctness scores than those using the Virtual Mode.)
- **RQ3:** Do performance differences between the Hybrid and Virtual modes diminish as participants are given more time to complete tasks? (**H3:** With longer time constraints, the correctness and time-to-completion metrics will converge between the two modes.)

These research questions aim to explore how physical and virtual representations complement each other in enhancing the comprehension of software metrics.

C. Participants and Settings

The experiment will involve at least 30 participants, recruited from educational institutions from all levels to ensure diversity. Participants will include students (from secondary

school and university), educators and researchers with experience in programming in Scratch. A pre-screening questionnaire will assess participants' familiarity with Scratch projects, basic programming concepts, and VR environments. While ensuring a balanced level of prior experience across groups, we acknowledge that simultaneous expertise in all areas may vary, particularly for educators. We will include participants who demonstrate at least intermediate-level knowledge in these areas will be included in the study to ensure a baseline understanding of the tasks.

Participant Selection Criteria: Participants will be selected based on their familiarity with Scratch programming or equivalent block-based environments and experience with software metrics (particularly code smells). The study will ensure a balanced distribution of prior VR experience across groups to minimize bias. Moreover, individuals with prior exposure to the specific tasks or visualizations will be excluded. Each participant will complete a demographic survey collecting information on age, gender, educational background, programming experience, and prior VR exposure. This data will help identify potential confounding variables and ensure a balanced expertise distribution across experimental conditions.

Experimental Settings: The experiment will be conducted in a controlled environment to minimize external distractions and ensure uniform conditions for all participants. The settings include:

- **Hardware:** A VR headset compatible with A-Frame applications (e.g., Meta Quest 3), a computer for running the VR application, and a physical 3D-printed model of the city metaphor.
- **Software:** An A-Frame-based VR visualization application displaying the city metaphor for Scratch projects, incorporating key software metrics such as code smells, structural complexity, and code quality indicators. Figure 1 shows an example of the city visualization made with BABIAXR in VR.
- **Physical Model:** textcoloraddedA 3D-printed representation of the city metaphor, designed to match with the structure the VR visualization in terms of layout and scale, ensuring consistency between the Hybrid and Virtual modes. Figure 2 shows an example of the city visualization of a Scratch project printed in 3D.
- **Task Interface:** A system for presenting tasks inside the VR scene, recording participant responses, and measuring time to task completion. This system will be the same for all the participants.

Participants will be randomly assigned to one of two experimental groups: Hybrid Mode (3D-printed model followed by VR visualization) or Virtual Mode (VR visualization only). Tasks will be presented in a random order to reduce potential learning effects and ensure fairness in task difficulty across conditions.

By designing the experiment to include a mix of participants from different backgrounds and ensuring a standardized setting, we aim to control for variability and provide reliable results that can be generalized to diverse user populations. The

Fig. 1: Example of a city visualization scene in BABIAXR.

Fig. 2: Example of a 3D printed Dr Scratch city.

controlled environment and pre-defined criteria for participant selection will help mitigate threats to internal validity, such as individual differences in familiarity with Scratch or VR technology.

Experimental Material: The experimental material includes the physical 3D-printed city models and the VR visualization created using BABIAXR, both representing the same metrics extracted from the Scratch dataset. The VR visualization will be deployed on an A-Frame-based platform compatible with modern VR headsets, while the 3D-printed models will provide a tangible representation of the same city metaphor. Additionally, task sheets and a digital interface will be used to present the comprehension tasks, record participant responses, and measure task completion times. This material ensures consistency and fairness across both experimental conditions.

D. Tools and Dataset

The tools utilized in this experiment serve two primary purposes: generating the dataset of Scratch projects with associated metrics and constructing the city metaphor for visualization in both 3D-printed and VR formats. These tools are critical for ensuring the consistency and validity of the experimental setup.

Dr. Scratch for Dataset Creation: Dr. Scratch [7] is an automated tool designed to evaluate Scratch projects by providing metrics related to code quality and programming practices. For this study, it will be used to mine a diverse

repository of public Scratch projects, extracting key metrics such as code smells, complexity indicators (e.g., number of sprites, scripts, and blocks), and project quality attributes (e.g., modularity, abstraction, and logic). A subset of projects will be selected to ensure diversity in complexity and quality, forming the basis for meaningful city metaphor representations in both 3D-printed models and VR visualizations using BABIAXR. This dataset enables the design of tasks that effectively evaluate participant comprehension across both experimental conditions.

BABIAXR for Visualization Construction: BABIAXR is a toolset for creating immersive 3D and VR visualizations of software systems. In this experiment, it will be used to transform metrics from Dr. Scratch into a cohesive city metaphor visualization. Features such as building height, color, and footprint will encode specific metric values, enabling the creation of both physical 3D-printed models for the Hybrid Mode and interactive VR environments for the Virtual Mode. These visualizations will allow participants to explore and analyze Scratch project metrics in an intuitive and engaging manner.

Integration and Consistency: To ensure consistency across the experimental conditions, the 3D-printed model and the VR visualization will be generated from the same dataset and share an identical layout and scale. This uniformity will allow participants to transition seamlessly between the physical and virtual representations in the Hybrid Mode and provide a fair comparison with the Virtual Mode. The combination of Dr. Scratch and BABIAXR enables a robust experimental setup by leveraging state-of-the-art tools for mining and visualizing software metrics. This ensures that the visualizations used in the experiment are both accurate and meaningful, providing a reliable foundation for evaluating participant comprehension.

E. Tasks

Participants will complete three types of tasks designed to evaluate their ability to comprehend and analyze software metrics represented through the city metaphor. These tasks are:

- **Locate Code Smells:** Identify specific code smells within the Scratch project, such as duplicated code or long scripts, by analyzing the city’s buildings and zones.
- **Analyze Project Structure:** Assess the modularity and complexity of the Scratch project by interpreting the relationships and connections between different buildings (representing sprites and scripts).
- **Summarize Project Quality:** Provide an overall evaluation of the Scratch project’s quality based on visual cues, such as building height, color, and density, encoding metrics like abstraction and logic.

Each task will be performed under three time constraints: 5, 10, and 15 minutes. Performance will be measured using two metrics: correctness (accuracy of responses) and time to task completion. Tasks are randomized across participants to ensure fairness and reduce learning effects.

F. Variables

The independent variable in this experiment is the visualization mode, which determines how participants interact with the city metaphor (Hybrid Mode: 3D-printed + VR, or Virtual Mode: VR only). The dependent variables are task performance metrics: correctness (accuracy of responses) and time to completion. Additionally, we consider confounding variables such as participants' experience with Scratch, VR, and programming, as these could influence the results.

In more detail, the variables used in this experiment are summarized in Table I.

G. Design

We will follow the *ACM SIGSOFT Empirical Standards* [43] for the experiment design, adhering to the guidelines for quantitative methods in experiments involving human participants. The study employs a *one-factor, two-level* design, where the independent variable is the visualization mode (Hybrid Mode or Virtual Mode). Tasks will be randomized across participants to minimize learning effects, and participants will be randomly assigned to one of the two conditions, using stratified random sampling, ensuring a balanced distribution of experience levels in Scratch and VR. Given the small sample size, this approach minimizes the risk of imbalanced expertise across groups. This approach ensures a balanced and unbiased comparison of the effectiveness and efficiency of the two visualization modes while satisfying all essential attributes and several desirable ones outlined in the standards.

H. Procedure

The experiment will begin with an introductory session where participants receive a training of the visualization and a briefing about the study's objectives and complete a consent form. Following this, they will fill out a pre-study questionnaire to collect demographic data and assess their experience with Scratch, programming, and VR. Participants assigned to the Hybrid Mode will interact with the 3D-printed model, up to 10 minutes, before using the VR visualization, while those in the Virtual Mode will directly use the VR application. Each participant will perform three randomized tasks under time constraints (5, 10, and 15 minutes) to evaluate correctness and time to completion.

During the experiment, responses and task completion times will be recorded digitally. After finishing the tasks, participants will provide qualitative feedback about their experience, including usability and clarity of the visualizations. The order of tasks and visualization settings will be randomized to minimize order effects, ensuring the validity of the results. The entire session for each participant is expected to last approximately 45 minutes.

I. Analysis Procedure

The collected data will be analyzed using statistical methods to evaluate the impact of the visualization mode on task performance. Mixed linear models will be employed to examine the effects of the independent variable (visualization

mode) on the dependent variables (correctness and time to completion), while controlling for confounding variables such as participants' experience with Scratch, programming, and VR. Non-parametric tests, such as the Mann-Whitney U test, will be used to compare performance metrics between the Hybrid and Virtual modes, ensuring robustness against non-normal data distributions. Additionally, we will analyze performance trends under different time constraints (5, 10, and 15 minutes) to explore whether the advantages of the Hybrid Mode diminish with longer task durations. Effect sizes will be calculated to assess the practical significance of the results, and qualitative feedback from participants will be thematically analyzed using Seaman *et al.* [44] method of software engineering, to provide additional insights into the usability and clarity of the visualizations.

IV. EXECUTION PLAN

The experiment will be carried out in three distinct phases to ensure its validity and replicability.

Preparation Phase: We will finalize the dataset of Scratch projects using Dr. Scratch and create the 3D-printed models and VR visualizations with BABIAXR. A pilot study will be conducted to validate the tasks, tools, and overall procedure. All materials, including task sheets and questionnaires, will be reviewed and finalized.

Execution Phase: Participants will complete the experiment in individual sessions, randomly assigned to either the Hybrid or Virtual Mode. Each session will include a briefing, task execution under controlled conditions, and a debriefing to gather qualitative feedback. Data collection will focus on task responses, completion times, and participant feedback.

Analysis Phase: Collected data will be analyzed using mixed linear models and non-parametric tests to evaluate the impact of the visualization mode on task performance. Confounding variables will be included in the analysis, and qualitative feedback will be thematically analyzed to gain additional insights.

This structured plan ensures systematic execution and reliable outcomes for answering the research questions.

V. THREATS TO VALIDITY

A. Internal Validity

Internal validity is related to uncontrolled factors that can influence the effectiveness. In our case it pertains to:

Subjects: A potential threat to validity arises from the variability in participants' backgrounds, particularly their familiarity with Scratch programming, VR, and software metrics. To address this, we will recruit a diverse set of participants and collect demographic data, including experience levels with Scratch and VR, through a pre-experiment questionnaire. This data will be used as covariates in the analysis to account for differences across participants. Additionally, random assignment to experimental conditions will ensure balanced groups.

Tasks: The design of tasks could introduce bias if they are not equally challenging or representative of real-world scenarios. To mitigate this, all tasks are derived from metrics

Variable Type	Name	Description	Scale
Independent	Setting	Visualization mode used for the task: Hybrid Mode (3D-printed + VR) or Virtual Mode (VR only).	Categorical: “Hybrid”, “Virtual”
Dependent	Correctness	Accuracy of the responses, measured as the percentage of correct answers.	Real number (0 to 100)
Dependent	TimeToComplete	Time taken to complete each task, measured in seconds.	Real number
Confounding	ExperienceScratch	Participants’ familiarity with Scratch programming.	Categorical: “None”, “Beginner”, “Intermediate”, “Advanced”
Confounding	ExperienceVR	Overall experience with VR devices, including frequency of use.	Categorical: “None”, “Low”, “Medium”, “High”
Confounding	ProgrammingExperience	General programming expertise, assessed in years of practice.	Integer number
Confounding	Role	Participants’ role, distinguishing between secondary school students, university students, educators and researchers.	Categorical: “Student A”, “Student B”, “Educator”, “Researcher”

TABLE I: Variables used in the experiment

commonly analyzed in Scratch projects, such as code smells and project structure. A pilot study will be conducted to validate the clarity, difficulty, and representativeness of the tasks. Randomization of task order for each participant will help prevent order effects and learning biases.

Training: Differences in how participants understand and use the experimental tools could impact results. To ensure consistency, all participants will receive the same standardized training before the experiment. This training will cover the use of the 3D-printed models and VR visualizations, as well as the interpretation of the city metaphor. Participants will also complete a practice task to familiarize themselves with the experimental setup before starting the actual tasks.

B. External Validity

External validity relates to the generalizability of the results of the experiment. In our case, it pertains to:

Sample Size. The number of participants in the experiment is limited to a minimum of 30. While this sample size is adequate for the planned statistical analyses, a larger sample could provide more robust and generalizable results. We will ensure that statistical tests are appropriately chosen to account for this limitation and will report effect sizes to assess the practical significance of the findings.

Subjects. The representativeness of the participant pool poses a potential threat, as the experiment involves a mix of students, educators, and researchers. To mitigate this, we will collect detailed demographic information, such as age, programming experience, and familiarity with Scratch, and ensure a balanced representation of these categories. This will help to make the findings applicable across diverse user groups.

Target Systems. The experiment focuses on Scratch projects, which may limit generalizability to other programming environments. To address this, we will select projects that represent a wide range of complexity and quality, ensuring that they reflect common challenges encountered in block-based programming. However, the results may not extend directly to textual programming environments or other software ecosystems.

Experimenter Effect. The experiment will be conducted by the authors of this research, which introduces the risk of bias in task evaluation or participant interaction. To reduce this threat, task solutions will be standardized and evaluated against predefined criteria. Additionally, qualitative feedback will be collected independently to ensure that subjective influences are minimized.

Time Measurement. External factors, such as interruptions or varying levels of concentration, could affect the time taken to complete tasks. To control this, participants will complete the experiment in a controlled environment free from distractions. Task times will be recorded automatically using a digital system to ensure consistency and accuracy.

VI. CONTRIBUTIONS AND IMPLICATIONS

This study contributes to the field of software visualization by evaluating the impact of hybrid visualizations—combining physical 3D-printed models and VR environments—on software comprehension. By focusing on Scratch projects and metrics such as code smells, the experiment bridges the gap between theoretical visualization approaches and practical applications in educational contexts (but relevant to industrial settings as well). The results are expected to provide empirical evidence on the benefits of hybrid visualization methods, particularly in time-constrained tasks.

The findings have significant implications for the design of software visualization tools. If the hybrid mode proves to enhance comprehension efficiency or accuracy, it could inform the integration of physical models into digital interfaces, optimizing cognitive processes and task performance. Additionally, analyzing performance across varying time constraints will offer insights into how physical and virtual representations complement each other, influencing future tool development for both novice and experienced users.

Beyond tool development, the study has broader implications for education and professional practices. Hybrid visualizations could make abstract software concepts more accessible to learners, particularly in block-based programming environments like Scratch. For practitioners, they could improve collaboration and decision-making when dealing with

complex software systems. Overall, this research highlights the value of hybrid approaches and lays the foundation for future exploration in combining physical and virtual interfaces to enhance software comprehension.

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